

Repository of morphological data for deep-sea faunal novelties

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Keywords: morphological data; deep-sea; fauna

MorphoBank has become my first choice for depositing morphological data associated with scientific publications. In this brief talk, I will share my experience using MorphoBank to archive morphological datasets from five published projects (P3629, P3801, P3840, P4108, P4854) and one unpublished project under consideration. The focus will be on the repository of morphological data for deep-sea and hadal faunal novelties. I will also discuss some experiences I encountered during the submission and peer review process.

Citation: Song, X. 2025. Repository of morphological data for deep-sea faunal novelties. MorphoBank Connects: virtual, September 18-19, 2025.